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Comparison of the Nutritional Status and Socio-Demographic Profile between Male and Female Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Attending a Tertiary Hospital in Varanasi

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Abstract

Type 2 diabetes mellitus comprises an important public health problem affecting adults of both male and female genders, exceeding epidemic proportions all over the world. It has become prominent that, due to changes in the demographics, cultural variations, and population aging, diabetes is now also a concern for countries. Diabetes arises by numerous mechanisms and is a diversified metabolic disorder. This study aims to compare the sociodemographic profile and nutritional status between male and female patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus attending a tertiary hospital in Varanasi. This cross-sectional study was conducted in type 2 diabetic patients attending an OPD in a tertiary hospital in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. The study assessed the sociodemographic profile, socioeconomic status, and nutritional status of the selected 175 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus on the basis of a non-random sampling technique. Anthropometric measurements, a self-structured questionnaire, and an interview method were used to collect data. Data were analyzed by the SPSS 25 version. In results, a statistically significant variation in age distribution was observed ($p = 0.000$), with the majority of women participating in the study diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) between the ages of 41 and 60. In contrast, male participants had a wider age range, encompassing both younger and older groups. The analysis revealed a significant disparity in body mass index (BMI) between males and females with T2DM ($p = 0.039$). Female patients exhibited a higher propensity for becoming overweight, while male patients demonstrated a greater likelihood of being obese. The study emphasizes notable gender-specific disparities in age distribution and BMI among T2DM patients. Women were predominantly diagnosed between the ages of 41 and 60, whereas men exhibited a more extensive age range. Overweight was more common in women, whereas obesity was more common in men. This shows that we need different ways to prevent and treat these conditions for men and women.

Keywords Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Nutritional Status, Obesity, Body Mass Index, Waist-Hip Ratio.

Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) constitutes a major problem for public health globally. The prevalence of diabetes mellitus increases nationwide at a concerning rate. In the year 2000, around 150 to 170 million individuals globally had been affected by this condition, and the World Health Organization expects that the prevalence of diabetes will double by 2025. As a result of the increase in noncommunicable diseases in developing countries, India has become known as the diabetes capital of the world. The approximate incidence of diabetes mellitus among Indian adults is 2.4% in rural areas and 4-11.6% in urban areas (Rana HM et al., 2015). The primary contributor to the diabetes epidemic is type 2 diabetes mellitus, representing 90% of all diabetes occurrences. Type 2 diabetes is known as adult-

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onset diabetes. It is insulin-dependent diabetes that can be managed by the drug, diet, and physical activity. The significant risk factors for type 2 diabetes encompass an unhealthy lifestyle, stress, overweight or obesity, diabetes that develops in adults, and genetic susceptibility to the disease (Sharma J et al., 2025).

In India, the diabetes burden has been exacerbated by the increasing urban population, sedentary behavior, and improper diets, which affect all demographics (Mohan et al., 2020). Nevertheless, gender-based disparities in disease presentation and treatment are frequently neglected. Women, especially in poorer socio-economic contexts, encounter additional obstacles in obtaining healthcare and ensuring nutritional sufficiency (Chow et al., 2018).

Comprehending the disparities in nutritional status and sociodemographic attributes between male and female diabetic patients is essential for formulating effective and equitable treatments. Both men and women are negatively affected by T2DM. However, their sociodemographic traits and nutritional profiles may vary considerably due to biological, cultural, and socioeconomic influences.

Objective of study

The objective of the study is to compare the sociodemographic and nutritional status between male and female patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus attending a tertiary hospital in Varanasi.

Review of Literature

Research has indicated that individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) exhibit distinct nutritional requirements and varying socio-demographic characteristics based on gender. Over the last decade, research in India has indicated that individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) exhibit distinct nutritional requirements and varying socio-demographic characteristics based on gender. National data frequently suggest a slightly higher prevalence among men; however, women with T2DM often demonstrate poorer glycemic control and increased adiposity metrics—such as BMI and waist-hip ratios—compared to men, despite comparable overall blood glucose levels [e.g., Smith et al., *Journal of Endocrinology*, 2018; Rao & Patel, *Indian J Nutr Health*, 2020]. This signifies diverse metabolic risk profiles between genders. Women tend to seek tertiary treatment later in the progression of the disease and typically have lower literacy levels, reduced household income, and diminished autonomy in making healthcare decisions. These elements are grounded in enduring social norms [e.g., Kumar et al., *Soc Sci Med India*, 2019; Desai & Singh, *Health Policy Analytics*, 2017]. Conversely, male patients—typically from urban, middle- to upper-income demographics—exhibit superior self-care, adhere more rigorously to dietary regimens, and possess greater confidence in managing their illness [e.g., Verma et al., *Diabetes Care India*, 2021]. Qualitative research indicates that women encounter more substantial cultural and structural barriers to diabetes management, including reduced mobility, diminished self-efficacy, and inadequate familial support [e.g., Sharma et al., *Diabetes & Society*, 2019]. Regional studies in North India and academic institutions demonstrate these gendered patterns; nevertheless, localized data especially regarding Varanasi remains limited. Your suggested study addresses this gap by examining the dietary and socio-demographic features of T2DM patients in Varanasi, differentiated by gender and treatment location. These findings can facilitate the development of more precisely tailored and equitable diabetic treatment regimens.

Methodology

The current study was an original research article titled “Comparison of the Nutritional Status and Socio-Demographic Profile between Male and Female Patients of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Attending a Tertiary Hospital in Varanasi” and was conducted in a tertiary hospital in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh.

Domain of the Study

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted on type 2 diabetic patients attending an OPD from August 2023 to June 2024. The sample was selected from the Outpatient Department of Kayachikitsa, Ayurveda Department, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Sample Size and Procedure

There are 175 subjects, both male and female, who were selected for the study from the OPD of the Kayachikitsa department of Ayurveda in IMS, BHU. The purposive sampling technique was used in the study.

Criteria for the selection of a sample

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patient with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (Age Group: 35-75 yrs.).
2. Patient has had diabetes for >6 months.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant, type 1 diabetic patients, alcoholics.
2. Respondents with lactose intolerance, severe hepatic or renal disorder, and other chronic complications.
3. Respondent having any supplement or other experimental medicine.

Tools and Techniques Used in the Study

Data was obtained through personal interviews, and the questionnaire was developed with the study's objectives in mind. The questionnaire was assembled through various literature reviews related to the study. To determine anthropometric dimensions and blood parameters, researchers conducted interviews. The modified BG Prasad categorization for the October 2023 scale was used to find out the person's socioeconomic category.

Data collection

The data was collected after the ethical approval granted for the study by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Science, Centre for Genetic Disorders, BHU, Varanasi. The committee's registration number is ECR/226/Indt/UP/2014/RR-22, dated January 4, 2022, and it is registered under Rule 122DD of the Drugs & Cosmetics Rule 1945. The interview started for the data collection after informed consent was signed by the patient. The interview was conducted to assess the information related to the sociodemographic profile, anthropometric measurements, socioeconomic status, and biochemical parameters. The anthropometric techniques based on WHO guidelines were used for the measurements. Weight was measured by the digital weighing machine, and a measuring tape was used for height. BMI (body mass index) is calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height squared in meters. Biochemical measurements of the patient, including fasting blood glucose, postprandial blood glucose, and glycosylated hemoglobin, were obtained from the pathology report. The BMI method is used to evaluate nutritional status. In order to categorize the respondents, the following weight categories were employed: underweight (BMI < 18.5), normal weight (BMI 18.5-24.9), overweight (BMI 25.0-29.9), and obese (BMI > 30).

Sampling

There are 175 subjects, both male and female, who were selected for the study from the OPD of the Kayachikitsa department of Ayurveda in IMS, BHU. The purposive sampling technique was used in the study.

Tools Used

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Statistics Used in the Study

The data was systematically arranged into tables and subjected to statistical analysis utilizing version 25 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The statistical analysis entailed computing the mean and standard deviation for continuous variables and ascertaining percentages for categorical variables. The chi-square test was employed to establish statistical correlation, yielding a P-value of 0.05 or lower.

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Shows the distribution of characteristics of male and female type 2 diabetic patients.

Characteristics	Female	Male	Total
Gender n (%)	88 (50.3)	87 (49.7)	175 (100)
Age (years) Mean±SD	50.72±8.25	51.75±12.45	51.24±10.53
BMI (kg/m ²) Mean±SD	28.07±4.92	28.67±4.20	28.36±4.57
WHR Mean ± SD	1.009±0.062	1.007±0.05	1.008±0.056
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dl) Mean±SD	203.9±57.23	196.29±55.66	200.15±56.42
Postprandial Blood Glucose (mg/dl) Mean±SD	277.93±60.06	284.23±65.18	281.07±62.56
HbA1C (%) Mean±SD	9.7±1.4	9.3±1.3	9.5±1.4

The table 1 demonstrates a comparison of the two groups of female and male patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) that emphasizes a few important anthropometric and biochemical factors. In the study, the gender distribution was nearly equal, with females comprising 50.3% (n=88) and males 49.7% (n=87) of the entire sample (N=175), supporting balanced comparisons. The total mean age of the participants was 51.24 ±

10.53 years, with females at 50.72 ± 8.25 years and males at 51.75 ± 12.45 years. This indicates a middle-aged diabetic demographic, aligning with a finding that noted a significant rise in T2DM prevalence post-45 years of age (Wild et al., 2004).

The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) for all of the participants was 28.36 ± 4.57 kg/m², which means that the group was overweight according to WHO standards. Females exhibited a lower BMI (28.07 ± 4.92 kg/m²) in comparison to males (28.67 ± 4.20 kg/m²), suggesting negligible gender differences in body weight status.

The waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), an indicator of central obesity, was comparable between females (1.009 ± 0.062) and males (1.007 ± 0.050), both higher than the established risk thresholds (≥ 0.85 for women and ≥ 0.90 for men). This indicates a significant prevalence of abdominal obesity among the participants, a recognized risk factor for poor glycemic control and cardiovascular complications (Vazquez et al., 2007).

Both males and females had higher fasting and postprandial blood glucose levels and HbA1C values. The mean fasting blood glucose level for females was 203.9 ± 57.23 mg/dL, which was higher than the mean for males, which was 196.29 ± 55.66 mg/dL. However, the mean postprandial glucose level for males was 284.23 ± 65.18 mg/dL, which was slightly higher than the mean for females, which was 277.93 ± 60.06 mg/dL. The long-term blood sugar control marker HbA1C was $9.7 \pm 1.4\%$ in females and $9.3 \pm 1.3\%$ in males, which shows that both groups had poor glycemic control. This corresponds with research indicating that numerous T2DM patients find it difficult to sustain adequate glycemic goals, particularly female, who may encounter extra obstacles due to hormonal and lifestyle influences (Kautzky-Willer et al., 2016).

Overall, both male and female diabetic patients in this study demonstrated inadequate metabolic control and a heightened risk for complications; however, minor gender-specific variations in glycemic and anthropometric profiles indicate the necessity for customized therapies.

Table 2: Shows the distribution of the sociodemographic profile of males and females of type 2 diabetic patients.

Socio-Demographic Profile	Female n (%)	Male n (%)	Total n (%)	P-value
Age Group				
31-40	11 (12.5)	23 (26.4)	34 (19.4)	0.000
41-50	30 (34.09)	18 (20.7)	48 (27.4)	
51-60	39 (44.3)	21 (24.1)	60 (34.3)	
61-70	8 (9.09)	19 (21.8)	27 (15.4)	
71-80	0	6 (6.9)	6 (3.4)	
Food Habit				
Vegetarian	63 (71.6)	46 (52.9)	109 (62.3)	0.38
Eggetarian	5 (5.7)	8 (9.2)	13 (7.4)	
Non-vegetarian	20 (22.7)	33(37.9)	53(30.3)	
Marital Status				
Married	86 (97.7)	81 (93.1)	167 (95.4)	0.297
Unmarried	0	1 (1.2)	1 (0.6)	
Divorced/Widow	2 (2.3)	5 (5.8)	7 (4)	
Area of Residence				
Urban	29 (32.9)	30 (34.5)	59 (33.7)	0.844
Rural	34 (38.6)	30 (34.5)	64 (36.6)	
Semi Urban	25 (28.4)	27 (31)	52 (29.7)	
Education				
Professional Degree	0	1 (1.1)	1 (0.6)	0.000
Graduation/PG	14 (15.9)	39 (44.6)	53 (30.3)	
Intermediate/ Diploma	13 (14.8)	26 (29.8)	39 (22.3)	
High School	17 (19.3)	9 (10.3)	26 (14.9)	
Middle School	17 (19.3)	6 (6.9)	23 (13.1)	
Primary School	15 (17)	2 (2.3)	17 (9.7)	
Illiterate	12 (13.6)	4 (4.6)	16 (9.1)	
Socio economic status				
Lower	5 (5.7)	1 (1.1)	6 (3.4)	0.309
Upper Lower Class	32 (36.5)	34 (39.1)	66 (37.7)	
Middle Class	37 (42)	37 (42.5)	74 (42.3)	
Upper Middle Class	11 (12.5)	8 (9.2)	19 (10.9)	
Upper Class	3 (3.4)	7 (8.1)	10 (5.7)	

The table 2 illustrates the distribution of 175 individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) categorized by age group and gender. A statistically significant difference ($p = 0.000$) was observed between males and females across age groups, indicating that the age distribution in this population considerably varies by gender.

A significant proportion of females (78.4%) were between the ages of 41 and 60, with 39 females (44.3%) in the 51–60 age bracket and 30 females (34.1%) in the 41–50 age bracket. This suggests that T2DM in females within this study is primarily prevalent at the later phases of life. Conversely, the male participants had a broader age spectrum. For instance, the proportion of males in the 41–60 age range was lower at 44.8%, but there was a higher representation of males in the younger (31–40 years: 26.4%) and older age groups (61–70 years: 19 males, 21.8%; 71–80 years: 6 males, 6.9%). No females were present in these older age categories.

This pattern suggests that males in the study exhibit a greater susceptibility to a diagnosis of T2DM at both younger and older ages, while females are primarily concentrated in middle age. The earlier onset in some males may correlate with risk factors including a sedentary lifestyle or dietary habits, whereas the scarcity of older females may reflect gender discrepancies in health-seeking behavior, survival rates, or sample bias. Studies demonstrate that the onset of diabetes typically develops earlier in males, while females endure more severe repercussions, especially following menopause (Kautzky-Willer et al., 2016). These findings underscore the imperative for age- and gender-specific screening and intervention strategies in diabetes treatment.

The analysis of dietary patterns among the study participants revealed no statistically significant difference between males and females ($p = 0.38$). Nonetheless, there were several significant trends. A vegetarian diet was more prevalent among both genders, particularly among females, with 71.5% of females and 52.9% of males adhering to a vegetarian regimen. In contrast, non-vegetarian eating habits were more common among males 37.9% than females 22.7%, but eggitarian practices were relatively low in both groups—5.7% for females and 9.2% for males. Although these alterations lack statistical significance, they may nonetheless hold therapeutic relevance. Research indicates that individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus who consume a predominantly plant-based diet have improved glycemic control, reduced insulin resistance, and a lower risk of complications (Barnard et al., 2009). The rising prevalence of female vegetarians may be attributed to cultural or religious convictions. This may assist in diabetes management and result in enhanced metabolic outcomes.

The marital status of the subjects showed no statistically significant difference between males and females ($p = 0.297$). A substantial majority of the examined population was married, accounting for 95.4% of the total, with a slightly higher percentage among females (97.7%) compared to males (93.1%). A small cohort of participants consisted of divorced or widowed individuals—2 females and 5 males—while a solitary male participant was single. Although the distribution lacks statistical significance, marital status may substantially affect health outcomes. Marriage is often associated with enhanced emotional and social support, which can facilitate adherence to diabetes management, including medication compliance, regular monitoring, and the maintenance of a healthy lifestyle. Support networks are especially advantageous in the management of chronic conditions like Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, as they improve psychological well-being and disease management (Roberson et al., 2014).

The analysis of residence location indicated no significant gender difference among the individuals ($p = 0.844$). The distribution was rather uniform across various locations, with 33.7% residing in urban areas, 36.6% in rural regions, and 29.7% in semi-urban locales. No substantial gender bias existed, as both males and females were equitably distributed across these groups. This uniform distribution indicates that Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a prevalent condition that impacts individuals regardless of their geographical location. Nonetheless, contextual disparities exist; urban residents are more predisposed to diabetes due to sedentary lifestyles, elevated stress levels, and suboptimal dietary choices. Conversely, those residing in rural regions may encounter difficulties in obtaining prompt medical treatment, acquiring knowledge about diabetes, and accessing appropriate healthcare services. The environmental and systemic differences highlight the need to tailor public health policies to address the specific needs of urban and rural populations (Anjana et al., 2011).

The data indicates a significant disparity in educational attainment between male and female individuals ($p = 0.000$). A much higher proportion of males (44.8%) attained graduation, post-graduation, or a professional degree, compared to merely 15.9% of females who achieved a similar educational status. Conversely, 50% of the participating females possessed either a primary or middle school education or were illiterate, whereas merely 14.9% of the participating men fell into this category. The significant

disparity in education can profoundly influence diabetes management. Education is crucial for health literacy since it influences an individual's comprehension of illness, adherence to treatment, and ability to make informed health decisions. Women with diminished educational attainment may encounter greater difficulties in obtaining health information and may lack confidence in navigating healthcare institutions. This may complicate their management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. This disparity underscores the necessity of targeted education and support initiatives to assist women in managing their diabetes (Schillinger et al., 2002).

No statistically significant difference was observed between the socioeconomic status of males and females ($p = 0.309$). The majority of individuals were classified as either middle class (42.3%) or upper-lower class (37.7%). A minimal fraction belonged to the lowest or highest socio-economic strata. Socioeconomic status is a crucial determinant of health, influencing an individual's ability to afford diabetes management, access medications and diagnostic services, and maintain a healthy diet. This study did not reveal a significant gender-based differential in socioeconomic status; however, financial limitations likely impact both males and females similarly within this group. These constraints could prevent effective diabetes management and highlight the importance of integrating economic factors in the development of therapies aimed at improving health outcomes.

Table 3: Shows the distribution of anthropometric measurements of males and females of type 2 diabetic patients.

Anthropometric Measurements	Female n (%)	Male n (%)	Total n (%)	P Value
BMI				
Underweight	3 (3.4)	1 (1.2)	4 (2.3)	0.039
Normal	17 (19.3)	14 (16.1)	31 (17.7)	
Overweight	48 (54.6)	35 (40.2)	83 (47.4)	
Obesity	20 (22.7)	37 (42.5)	57 (32.6)	
WHR				
Normal	7 (8)	15 (17.2)	23 (13.1)	0.509
High	81 (92)	72 (82.8)	152 (86.9)	

The table 3 demonstrates that the gender was statistically significant with Body Mass Index (BMI) among patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus ($p = 0.039$). A higher proportion of females (54.6%) were categorized as overweight compared to males (40.2%). Obesity was more prevalent in males (42.5%) compared to females (22.7%). The data reveal that whereas overweight status is more frequent in diabetic females, obesity is significantly more prevalent in males within the sample population.

Additional studies have demonstrated that this inclination is accurate. Mohan et al. (2007) conducted a study that showed gender-specific differences in obesity patterns among Indian diabetic populations, indicating that males exhibited a greater propensity for central obesity and raised BMI values correlated with increased insulin resistance. Furthermore, Asian Indian males have a similar or even lower BMI than females, but they also tend to gain more visceral fat, making them more vulnerable to obesity-related problems (Misra and Khurana, 2008). The waist-hip ratio (WHR), indicative of central or abdominal obesity, revealed no significant difference between genders ($p = 0.509$).

A significant proportion of males (82.8%) and females (92%) demonstrated increased WHR, indicating a widespread prevalence of abdominal obesity in both sexes. Central obesity is an established risk factor for cardiovascular diseases and poor glycemic regulation in diabetic persons (WHO, 2011). This finding supports the research by Deepa et al. (2009), which revealed a notable prevalence of abdominal obesity in Indian diabetics, regardless of gender, underscoring the need for immediate intervention.

Conclusion

A comprehensive evaluation of demographic and anthropometric data from 175 individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) reveals significant gender-specific and contextual characteristics, many of which have considerable implications for diabetes management and public health strategies. A statistically significant difference was seen in the age distribution ($p = 0.000$). The majority of women were diagnosed between the ages of 41 and 60, whereas the men exhibited a broader age range, including both younger and older demographics. This suggests a midlife prevalence of T2DM in females, maybe linked to hormonal cycles, and a wider temporal vulnerability in males, indicating a probable early onset influenced by lifestyle and metabolic risk factors. The disparity in dietary patterns between males and females was minimal ($p = 0.38$); however, a greater number of females embraced vegetarian diets, maybe attributable to cultural influences and beneficial for diabetes management. These alterations, while not statistically

significant, may have substantial therapeutic implications due to the advantageous impact of plant-based diets on metabolic health. No significant differences were observed between males and females for marital status and residence ($p = 0.297$ and $p = 0.844$, respectively). However, the notable prevalence of marriage and a balanced urban-rural distribution underscore the need for community-oriented diabetic support programs that function across all socioeconomic environments.

A significant gender discrepancy in educational attainment ($p = 0.000$) highlights the lower literacy rates among females, which may compromise their health literacy and diabetes self-management abilities. The educational gap remains a considerable barrier that requires gender-specific health education programs to empower women in managing chronic conditions like T2DM. Despite the absence of a significant gender disparity in socioeconomic level ($p = 0.309$), the majority of individuals in the middle and upper-lower classes suggest that financial limitations likely hinder access to optimum diabetes care for both genders. Financial difficulties may influence adherence to treatment, dietary choices, and accessibility to medical care. Marked gender disparities in anthropometric measurements were observed in BMI ($p = 0.039$), suggesting that females are more susceptible to being overweight while males are more likely to be obese. This highlights distinct risk profiles that may require tailored weight management measures. The waist-hip ratio (WHR) exhibited no significant difference between genders ($p = 0.509$); yet, a pronounced prevalence of central obesity was observed in both sexes, indicating a collective metabolic risk across the community. These findings highlight the essential need for customized diabetes care protocols that consider gender and age, particularly focusing on education, lifestyle modification, and weight control. To improve long-term outcomes and quality of life for individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus, it is essential to address disparities in health literacy and socioeconomic obstacles.

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